

Cardiovascular Risk and Hepatic Steatosis in Patients Treated at A Level 2 Hospital

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ABSTRACT

Background: Hepatic steatosis, currently recognized as a metabolic liver disease, is linked to the global epidemic of obesity, insulin resistance, type 2 diabetes, metabolic syndrome, and cardiovascular disorders. Cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of death worldwide. From a pathophysiological perspective, the accumulation of intrahepatic lipids is associated with chronic low-grade inflammation, oxidative stress, endothelial dysfunction, and activation for the development of atherosclerosis. These alterations result in an increased risk of ischemic heart disease and cardiovascular disease. Imaging plays a role in the non-invasive detection of hepatic steatosis in its different stages using abdominal ultrasound and in the evaluation of cardiovascular risk markers using cardiac computed tomography, as well as in the identification of atherosclerotic calcifications of the coronary arteries.

General objective: To determine the association between cardiovascular risk and the degree of hepatic steatosis in patients treated at HGRO No 1.

Material and methods: This is a cross-sectional, observational, prospective, and analytical study. Non-random quota sampling was used. Frequencies and percentages were obtained for qualitative variables, and measures of central tendency and dispersion were obtained for quantitative variables. The chi-square test was used for inferential statistics, achieving statistical significance with a p-value <0.05. The sample consisted of 250 patients with hepatic steatosis of varying degrees, who underwent cardiac tomography between May 2025 and July 2025 at HGRO 01.

Results: This study included 250 patients, of whom 139 (56.6%) were women. The mean age was 50.02 years. Obesity was the predominant BMI in 89 patients (35.6%). Hypertension and diabetes mellitus were found in 87 patients (34.8%) and 85 patients (34%), respectively. Mild hepatic steatosis was the most prevalent, found in 98 patients (39.3%), and very low cardiovascular risk was the most common, found in 96 patients (38.4%), with a statistically significant association ($X^2 = 12.82$, $p = 0.046$).

Conclusions: Cardiovascular risk is directly associated with the degree of hepatic steatosis, as a higher degree of hepatic steatosis was associated with a greater cardiovascular risk. Therefore, the alternative hypothesis can be confirmed, and the null hypothesis rejected. A high frequency of overweight and obesity was found. Furthermore, it can be concluded that diabetes mellitus and hypertension are important factors in this pathology.

KEYWORDS: Risk factors, hepatic steatosis, cardiovascular risk, coronary calcium score.

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INTRODUCTION

Cardiovascular disease is the leading cause of death worldwide, and its development often begins subclinically

years before clinical events appear. Therefore, early identification of markers of subclinical atherosclerosis and

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cardiovascular risk is essential for risk stratification and primary prevention ^(1,2).

Hepatic steatosis of metabolic origin is the most common chronic liver disease and is closely associated with insulin resistance, dyslipidemia, visceral obesity, and systemic inflammation—factors directly involved in the development of atherosclerosis. In this context, hepatic steatosis has been recognized not only as a liver disease but also as a systemic marker of cardiometabolic risk ^(3,4).

Abdominal ultrasound is the first-line imaging method for detecting hepatic steatosis due to its wide availability, low cost, and absence of ionizing radiation. Its diagnosis is based on diffuse increase in hepatic echogenicity, posterior attenuation of the ultrasound beam, and decreased visualization of intrahepatic vascular structures ⁽⁵⁾.

On the other hand, computed tomography with coronary calcium scoring using the Agaston method is the validated marker of coronary atherosclerosis and a predictor of major cardiovascular events. Its use allows for more precise cardiovascular risk staging, specifically in patients with intermediate risk ^(5,6).

Since both imaging studies are widely used in medical practice, it is relevant to evaluate the correlation between the degrees of hepatic steatosis by ultrasound and the coronary calcium score determined by computed tomography, to demonstrate this association that allows positioning hepatic steatosis as an accessible indicator of subclinical cardiovascular risk and contribute to the early identification of patients with a higher probability of coronary atherosclerotic disease ⁽⁶⁾.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Coronary heart disease was the leading cause of death worldwide in 2023. It is a disease that increases alterations in lipid metabolism, leading to a higher risk of acute myocardial infarction. In Mexico, approximately 220,000 people died from cardiovascular diseases in 2021, of which 177,000 were due to myocardial infarction. This condition can be prevented by avoiding or controlling risk factors such as smoking, high blood pressure, high cholesterol, and uncontrolled diabetes. While this disease is closely related to various metabolic disorders, it is also associated with coronary artery disease. Therefore, in cardiology practice, computed tomography is a non-invasive diagnostic method for coronary artery disease in patients with mild or moderate cardiovascular risk factors, through the calculation of a calcium score. ^(6,7,8)

The coronary calcium score (CCS) is a quantitative measure used to assess the calcium burden in the coronary arteries using computed tomography (CT). It is a very useful tool because it allows for the detection of subclinical arteriosclerosis, the stratification of individuals according to their risk of cardiovascular events, and, unlike clinical cardiovascular risk scores, it is a direct measure of atherosclerotic disease. ⁽⁹⁾

CT scans for SCC calculation can be performed on most scanners. As a general principle, protocols using the lowest possible dose of ionizing radiation are always employed, and for prospective studies, the mean effective dose should be approximately 1.0–1.5 mSv. The total scan time is short, approximately 10–15 minutes. The acquisition protocol typically used in helical CT usually has the following specifications: Scanners with at least 8 detector rows, prospective electrocardiographic gating, slice thickness of 2.5–3 mm, and an interval of 1 mm. Acquisition should extend from the inferior aspect of the aortic arch to below the base of the heart. Kilovoltage: 120 kV. Milliampères: dependent on body mass index. Reconstructions: soft tissue and lung filters. ^(10,11)

A review conducted in 2023 determined the SCC indications and recommendations of seven societies worldwide, including recommendations from societies in North America, Europe, Australia, New Zealand, China, and Japan, as well as other specialized societies. ⁽¹²⁾

The SCC is a specific marker of subclinical atherosclerosis and is important for risk stratification and therapeutic decision-making. Following the recommendations of the coronary computed tomography calcium score (CCCS) We can stratify the SCC results based on the Agatston score as follows: 0 very low risk, 1-10 = minimal, 11-100 = slight risk, 101-400 = moderate risk, More than 400 = severe risk ⁽¹³⁾

Scoring methods like the Agatston method give more weight in the final score to denser calcifications, even though some studies have shown that these plaques are more stable compared to less dense ones. Furthermore, since the cutoff for detecting calcium in this method is 130 HU, results must be taken and correlated with medical history and biochemical data to avoid overlooking microcalcifications, which are not included in early detection. ⁽¹⁴⁾

Finally, there is a cost-effectiveness benefit of SCC in guiding statin therapy, as SCC-guided statin initiation compared to universal statin therapy has a virtually cost-neutral effect at 5 years and is cost-effective at 10 years for patients at intermediate risk of cardiovascular disease. ⁽¹⁵⁾

The indications varied in some aspects among the different societies, but most guidelines agree on two points: The SCC is indicated in patients over 40 years of age, with intermediate risk and who are asymptomatic, and an SCC of 0 is used to lower the risk category and avoid initiating statin treatment, while an SCC greater than 100 indicates that initiating statin treatment should be considered. On the other hand, the points of disagreement lie in the use of the SCC to initiate aspirin treatment and for the treatment of hypertension. ⁽¹⁶⁾

In a consensus statement from the American College of Cardiology/American Heart Association, after reviewing data from six large studies that collectively included 27,622 symptomatic patients, the relative risk of major cardiovascular events was measured. For this purpose, patients with a coronary artery calcium (CAC) score were

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compared to those with a CAC score of zero. The following results were observed: When the CAC score was obtained in patients of 100-400, the relative risk was 4.3 (95% CI: 3.1-6.1) of experiencing cardiovascular events compared to those with a score of 0; Similarly, those who obtained a CAC score of 401-999 had a relative risk of 7.2 (95% CI: 5.2-9.9), and finally, those who obtained a CAC score of 1000 had a relative risk of 10.8 (95% CI: 4.2-27.7).⁽¹⁷⁾

SCC may also be associated with an increased risk of non-cardiovascular diseases since patients with elevated SCC (> 400) have a higher risk of developing cancer, chronic kidney disease, chronic obstructive pulmonary disease, pneumonia and hip fractures⁽¹⁸⁾

Similarly, elevated coronary artery calcium scores in subjects without prior atherosclerotic disease have been shown to be associated with increased cardiovascular risk. In a cohort study by Budoff et al., they compared event rates in patients with arterial atherosclerosis. They established event rates in individuals without a history of atherosclerosis and calcium scores to determine at what level elevated arterial calcium scores equate to the risk associated with existing cardiac atherosclerosis. They selected 4,949 patients and compared them with 438 individuals with established atherosclerotic disease. Arterial calcium scores were categorized as 0, 1 to 100, 101 to 300, and >300. As a result, the mean age was 57.6 ± 12.4 years (56% male), and 442 of the 4,949 (9%) patients underwent revascularization during a median follow-up of 4 years. They observed that revascularizations increased with higher arterial calcium scores^(19,20).

A cohort study by Shaw LJ et al., which followed 25,253 asymptomatic patients for approximately 7 years and assessed the SCC score, among other parameters, demonstrated that the SCC was an independent predictor of mortality. Furthermore, adding the SCC score to other traditional cardiovascular risk factors significantly increased its predictive capacity for events. The risk of cardiovascular mortality compared to individuals with an SCC score of 0 was directly proportional to the increase in the SCC score. Scores between 101 and 299 were associated with a 4.5-fold increased risk; between 300 and 399, a 6.4-fold increased risk; between 400 and 699, a 9.2-fold increased risk; between 700 and 999, a 10.4-fold increased risk; and scores above 1000, an increased risk of up to 12.5 times, all statistically significant.⁽²¹⁾

Kirby RS et al., a cross-sectional study recruited 134 patients with a mean age of 62 years (SD 9.1), 65% male, with a body mass index of 28.5 (SD 6.0) and 8% diabetic. A relationship was observed between hepatic steatosis, severity of coronary artery disease, body mass index greater than 30 with odds ratio 6.77 (95% CI: 1.40-32.66, $p = 0.02$) and diabetes with odds ratio 9.60 (95% CI: 0.56-165.5, $p = 0.01$).⁽²²⁾

As mentioned, the measurement of atherosclerotic plaque using the calcium score suggests that the risk of vascular events in patients with metabolic diseases such as hepatic steatosis, and potentiated by diabetes, is higher, since they

present a risk of cardiovascular disease. similar to those of patients with a clinical history of atherosclerotic disease. Despite the higher cardiovascular risk and greater prevalence of ischemia as measured by functional tests, there is no evidence that Routine screening for silent ischemia reduces mortality in this patient group. The presence of any degree of coronary artery disease (CAD) in patients with diabetes mellitus translates into a higher risk of death from all causes. than in patients without diabetes.^(23,24)

The above was observed by Kramer et al. in a meta-analysis of eight studies comparing 6,521 patients. They found that individuals with diabetes and a CAC score < 10 were 6.8 times less susceptible to all-cause mortality and cardiovascular events, as well as cardiovascular events alone, than those with diabetes and a CAC score > 10. Similarly, a CAC score > 10 was associated with a higher risk of mortality and cardiovascular disease.⁽²⁵⁾

Kim, Sh conducted a cross-sectional study that included 7,259 participants in the non-alcoholic fatty liver disease (NAFLD) study. Participants had been assessed for coronary artery disease (CAD) and fatty liver status using a medical records database. The study compared the history of cardiovascular disease and whether this association differed according to sex and obesity status, adjusting for other atherosclerosis risk factors, alcohol intake, and liver enzyme levels. CAD scores were calculated using computed tomography. NAFLD was diagnosed in patients with evidence of hepatic steatosis on ultrasound. Obesity was defined as a body mass index (BMI) ≥25 kg/m². The analysis showed a significant association between NAFLD and CAD in non-obese participants (odds ratio, 1.24 [95% CI, 1.01-1.53]). Interaction analysis showed that the association between NAFLD and CAC was influenced by sex and obesity. Subgroup analysis revealed a significant association between NAFLD and CAC in non-obese male participants (odds ratio, 1.36 [1.07-1.75]), but not in women. The study concluded that non-obese men with NAFLD are prone to CAC.⁽²⁶⁾

As previously mentioned, the calcium score has also proven highly useful for the diagnosis and prognosis of coronary artery disease. Akiko F et al. conducted a retrospective study to develop and validate an optical coherence tomography (OCT)-based calcium scoring system to predict insufficient stent expansion. A calcium score was developed using pre- and post-stent OCT scans of 128 patients (cohort study) and subsequently validated in an external cohort of 133 patients. The results in the validation cohort demonstrated that lesions with a calcium score of 0 to 3 exhibited excellent stent expansion, while lesions with a score of 4 showed poor stent expansion (96% vs. 78%, $p < 0.01$). In conclusion, an OCT-based calcium scoring system can help identify lesions that would benefit from plaque modification before stent implantation. Lesions with calcium deposits with a maximum angle > 180°, maximum thickness > 0.5 mm and length > 5 mm may be at risk of stent expansion.⁽²⁷⁾

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Choi et al . conducted a study to investigate the role of coronary artery calcium (CAC) scoring as a screening tool for asymptomatic but severe atherosclerotic disease (ADD) in patients with acute stroke. The study included 2,658 consecutive patients with acute stroke who had undergone cerebral angiography and coronary angiography by multidetector computed tomography . A total of 192 AD and 228 cognitively normal (CN) subjects were identified. Severe AD was present in 360 patients (13.5%). The CAC score was associated with the severity of AD ($p < 0.001$). They concluded that the need for CAC assessment could be determined based on the presence of risk factors and significant cervicocephalic artery stenosis . CAC assessment may be useful for detecting severe AD in stroke patients. ⁽²⁸⁾

Williams conducted a study to evaluate whether the non-calcified low-attenuation plaque burden on coronary computed tomography angiography (CCTA) could be a better predictor of future myocardial infarction risk. A multicenter randomized controlled trial of CCTA in patients with stable chest pain was used. The results showed that in 1769 patients (56% male; 58 ± 10 years) followed for a median of 4.7 (interquartile range, 4.0–5.7) years, the low-attenuation plaque burden was weakly correlated with cardiovascular risk score. They concluded that in patients with stable chest pain, the low-attenuation plaque burden is the strongest predictor of fatal or non-fatal myocardial infarction. ⁽²⁹⁾

Cruz-Figeroa conducted an analytical observational study of 820 patients with chest pain who underwent Calcium Score assessment. A logistic regression model was applied to each of the measured coronary vessels. Each model was fitted to the variables, and Wald's test was used to identify those with coefficients significantly different from 0 ($p < 0.05$). The patients were predominantly over 60 years of age and male, with hypertension being the most frequent risk factor. The mathematical models for each coronary vessel excluded age, while the other variables were included. Diabetes and smoking were the most significant predictors. Internal validation techniques support the good performance of the mathematical models obtained. The results reinforce the need for predictive studies that guarantee cardiovascular risk stratification using Calcium Score and its risk factors. ⁽³⁰⁾

JUSTIFICATION

Cardiovascular diseases due to atherosclerosis are a latent problem in healthcare institutions. This type of condition often goes undetected because the prevalence of structural damage in micro and macro blood vessels is not precisely known; therefore, it is essential to establish care protocols for patients who appear to have this disease.

This study enabled specialist physicians and family members to expand their understanding of the cardiovascular risk in patients with hepatic steatosis, with the aim of strengthening comprehensive and preventative therapeutic decisions. Furthermore, it will provide clinical support for the importance of conducting complementary studies to reduce

complications, the risk of disability, or even death from coronary artery disease.

This research clarified non-invasive diagnostic alternatives for the early diagnosis of cardiovascular conditions and thus indirectly reduced costs for hospital care, disability in patients of working age, risk of suffering from healthcare-associated infections, among others.

Similarly, knowledge about the association of the disease and tomographic findings was expanded, because even though there is evidence of this; the association of each of the degrees of hepatic steatosis with the calcium score is not specified and that from them the hospital can establish comprehensive therapeutic managements in these patients.

PROBLEM STATEMENT

It is important to point out that cardiovascular diseases are increasingly common in patients in their forties, considered the economically active stage of life. This leads to a growing burden of disease and an increase in healthy life expectancy, which directly impacts the economic sectors of companies due to extended periods of disability or even job losses in high-productivity, socially impactful positions. Similarly, these diseases are becoming prevalent in the elderly, a stage of life characterized by high vulnerability to various illnesses that affect their structural and physiological well-being.

The above is due to various diseases that are increasingly appearing in early stages of life, such as diabetes, dyslipidemia, hypertension, among others, which are the result of poor diet and sedentary lifestyle, a serious repercussion that is sometimes reflected in catastrophic signs for health, or that occur in damage to vital organs such as the liver, heart, brain or kidneys.

When suffering from hepatic steatosis, it is imminent to establish whether there is a cardiovascular risk, since the latter has a discouraging outcome, and if it is not detected in time or if there is no visual overview of the damage conditioned to large vessels, it could only lead to incomplete treatments in a timely manner.

The diagnostic methods used to detect these diseases are life-threatening treatments that are invasive, difficult to obtain, or expensive. Therefore, our institution conducts active surveillance aimed at the timely identification of cases for immediate treatment, with the goal of optimal resolution of the condition. However, this approach can be modified by various clinical attributes of interest that characterize the patients, which may lead to longer recovery times and, consequently, extended periods of work disability, impacting our financial resources.

It is important to note that the epidemiological transition could favor an increase in the incidence rate of these diseases. Therefore, the following research question is posed:

What is the association between cardiovascular risk and hepatic steatosis in patients treated at a secondary care hospital?

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GOALS

GENERAL OBJECTIVE:

1. To determine the association between cardiovascular risk and the degree of hepatic steatosis in patients treated at the Regional General Hospital No. 1 of Orizaba Veracruz.

SPECIFIC OBJECTIVES

1. Classify patients according to their age and sex.
2. Determine the BMI and blood pressure of the patients.
3. Classify the degree of hepatic steatosis in patients using ultrasound.
4. Assess cardiovascular risk using simple cardiac tomography in patients.

HYPOTHESIS

- **Alternative hypothesis:**
 - Cardiovascular risk is associated with the degree of hepatic steatosis found in patients.
- **Null hypothesis:**
 - Cardiovascular risk is not associated with the degree of hepatic steatosis found in patients.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design: It is a cross-sectional, observational, prospective, and analytical study. Non-random quota sampling.

Study location: Regional General Hospital No. 1 Orizaba

Period to be developed: During May 2025- July 2025.

Work universe: Patients who sought medical attention at the Orizaba Regional General Hospital 1.

Population: Patients who sought medical attention and who were shown to have hepatic steatosis by ultrasound.

Selection criteria:

- **Inclusion:**
 - Patients diagnosed with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease by ultrasound treated at HGRO 01.
 - Patients who have a simple cardiac CT scan.
- **Exclusion:**
 - Those with a history or sequelae of cardiac and/or cerebral ischemic events.
 - Patients diagnosed with alcoholic hepatic steatosis.
- **Elimination:**
 - Patients who do not have a physical or electronic record for data consultation.

Definition of variables:

Dependent variable:

Variable name	Conceptual definition	Operational definition	Variable type and measurement scale	Indicator or index
Cardiovascular risk	It is the probability that a person will suffer from cardiovascular disease in a given period of time.	It will be identified by means of simple cardiac tomography obtained with the Agaston coronary calcium score .	Qualitative Ordinal	1. None; Very low risk of future coronary events 2. Mild; Low risk of future coronary events. 3. Moderate; Higher risk of future coronary events 4. Severe; higher probability of myocardial ischemia

Independent Variables:

Variable name	Conceptual description	Operational definition	Type of variable and measurement scale.	Indicator or index
Age	Exact time that has elapsed from birth to a specific moment.	Number of years completed, recorded in the clinical record during the study period.	Quantitative Discreet	Years

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Sex	Biological category that distinguishes individuals based on their anatomical, genetic, and hormonal characteristics.	Biological Category recorded in the clinical record at the time of the study.	Qualitative Nominal	1. Man 2. Women
Comorbidities	Simultaneous presence of two or more diseases or medical conditions in the same patient.	Diseases recorded in the clinical record at the time of the study	Qualitative Nominal	1. Diabetes 2. High Blood Pressure 3. Dyslipidemia
Body mass index (BMI)	Nutritional status indicator based on the relationship between weight and height.	Relationship between weight and height recorded in the clinical record at the time of the study.	Quantitative Continue	Kg/m ²
Nutrition grade	Categorization of a person's nutritional status based on their BMI.	Categorization according to BMI 1. Low weight (BMI < 18.5) 2. Normal weight (BMI 18.5 - 24.9) 3. Overweight (BMI 25.0 - 29.9) 4. Obesity (BMI ≥ 30.0)	Qualitative Ordinal	1. Low weight 2. Normal weight 3. Overweight 4. Obesity
Blood pressure	Blood pressure is the measurement of the pressure in the arteries when the heart contracts and pumps blood to the rest of the body.	Blood pressure measurement recorded in the medical record at the time of the study	Quantitative Discreet	mm Hg
Hepatic steatosis	It is a disease characterized by the accumulation of lipids in the liver.	The accumulation of lipids in the liver will be demonstrated by ultrasound and classified as Mild: minimal diffuse increase in hepatic echogenicity; normal visualization of the diaphragm and the border of the intrahepatic vessels. Moderate: diffuse increase in hepatic echogenicity; slight loss of visualization of intrahepatic vessels	Qualitative Ordinal	1. Mild 2. Moderate 3. Severe

and diaphragm.
Severe: marked
increase in
echogenicity; poor
penetration of the
posterior segment of
the right lobe and
poor visualization of
the diaphragm and
intrahepatic vessels.

Study overview:

Following the approval of the Research Ethics Committee and the Health Research Committee 3101 of the Regional General Hospital No. 1 of Orizaba with institutional registration number R-2025-3101-0311.

A search was conducted for patients diagnosed with fatty liver disease who were treated during May, June, and July of 2025. Patient data were listed and assigned an ascending number, starting with 1 and ending with the last patient registered in the hospital admissions. These numbers were then entered into an Excel spreadsheet, and patients were selected randomly. Once selected, their medical records were retrieved from the electronic health record. If a liver ultrasound was unavailable, one was performed to classify the degree of hepatic steatosis, until the sample was complete. After obtaining informed consent, each patient underwent a cardiac CT scan to identify coronary structures and estimate coronary calcium scores. A form-type instrument was used to collect clinical and radiological data. Clinical data were obtained from the medical progress notes in the electronic health record through the Hospitalization Platform of the Digital Health Ecosystem (PHEDS) or ECE MoCE . The information obtained from the questionnaires was captured by the researchers using computer equipment in a spreadsheet (Excel) previously prepared for this purpose . The captured information was analyzed using the GraphPad Prism program to perform univariate and bivariate analysis .

Sample

Sample size calculation:

For the calculation of the sample size, the formula for prevalence studies for infinite populations was used, with a known proportion of hepatic steatosis in the general population of 20% in previous studies, considering a confidence interval of 95%, with a statistical power of 80% and a precision of 5%.

Formula:

$$\text{Tamaño de la Muestra} = \frac{Z^2 p(1 - p)}{e^2}$$

where:

n = sample size 250

Z = critical Z value 1.96

p = approximate proportion of the phenomenon under study in the reference population 20%

q = proportion of the reference population that does not present the phenomenon under study 80%

d = absolute precision level of 0.05

This study will consider a sample of 250 participants.

Sampling:

The type of sampling that was applied was simple random probabilistic sampling.

Data analysis and statistical aspects:

Data collection was done through an electronic form, subsequently the information was organized into contingency tables to create a database with the help of statistical programs: Microsoft Excel 2019, GraphPad Prism Program with which the data analysis was carried out as follows:

I. Univariate analysis (Descriptive statistics)

Qualitative variables were expressed as simple frequencies and percentages. For quantitative variables, measures of central tendency and dispersion were used.

II. Bivariate analysis

The Fisher's exact test or the Chi-square test for comparing categorical variables was applied to qualitative variables. A p-value less than or equal to 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

GraphPad Prisma 8 program was used to present the data , creating graphs of results based on the type of variable.

ETHICAL ASPECTS

The research that was carried out complied with the specifications of NOM-012-SSA3-2012, which establishes the criteria for the execution of health research projects in human beings.

In accordance with the provisions of articles 57 and 58 of the General Health Law (LGS); therefore, participation in this research was voluntary, the information generated may be useful for future research that may have a benefit in health care, and does not represent legal harm to the person involved in it.

In our study, patient data was collected using non-invasive methods through documentary review of clinical records. Based on the provisions of Article 17 of the LGS regulations, it is classified as "Research with minimal risk " and compromises the confidentiality of the participants' data. Prior to its application, this study will be submitted for review

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by the ethics and research committees for approval; once it is accepted, it will begin to be carried out.

The research complies with the main purposes of medical research in human beings, as stated in the Declaration of Helsinki; because the information will be strictly confidential and will be protected with alphanumeric keys and the databases will be protected by an access key, only the research team will have access to the information, when the results of this study are published or presented in forums or conferences there is no information that could reveal the identity of the participants.

In this research, information from clinical records and electronic records will not be required, therefore obtaining informed consent from those involved will not be necessary. Based on what is described in the Nuremberg Code and the Belmont Report, the investigation will be carried out adopting the recommendations indicated.

In this research, the principle of beneficence is emphasized by highlighting the importance of identifying factors associated with the occurrence of ischemic cardiac events in patients with high cardiovascular risk, who are likely to benefit from close observation and early intervention with supportive therapy.

The direct benefit will be to identify the factors associated with the presentation of ischemic cardiac events, in order to

create clinical scenarios that will guide decision-making for the prevention and in-hospital management of this condition. During this study, the sample will be drawn from the electronic medical records of patients treated at Regional General Hospital No. 1 in Orizaba. The selection will be random, ensuring fairness and equity, and will not involve any form of discrimination. To safeguard the physical and mental well-being of the patients, all information will be obtained from the medical records during the application of our instrument, without any invasive procedures.

The present research is justified on the basis of a favorable assessment of risks and benefits, and is closely related to the principle of beneficence; likewise, the moral requirement to obtain informed consent is derived primarily from the principle of respect for persons.

RESULTS

The study consisted of a sample of 250 patients with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease diagnosed by ultrasound at the Orizaba Regional General Hospital. The patients were classified according to their sex, with 111 patients (44.4%) being male, while the remaining 139 patients (56.6%) were female (see Graph 1).

Chart 1. Sex of patients

The predominant sex was female, with 56.6%. n=250.

Regarding the age of the patients, it was determined that the mean age was 50.02 years (95% CI 47.92 – 52.13) with a standard deviation of +/-16.89, it was found that the minimum

age of the patients who belonged to this study was 16 years, while the maximum age found was 80 years, presenting a range of 64 years (see Graph 2).

Figure 2. Age distribution of patients

Age distribution $n=250$; $\bar{x}=50.02$; $\sigma = 16.89$.
 The BMI of the patients was determined, obtaining a mean of 28.14 (95% CI 27.48 – 28.81) with a standard deviation of ± 5.313 . The BMI ranged from a minimum of 18.07 to a maximum of 45.54, with a range of 27.47. The patients were

classified according to their BMI, where it was observed that 81 patients (32.4%) had a normal weight, 80 patients (32%) were overweight, and 89 patients (35.6%) presented some degree of obesity (see Graph 3).

Figure 3. BMI of patients

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Obesity was found in 89 patients (35.6%). n: 250.

The blood pressure of the patients was determined, where the maximum systolic blood pressure was 140mmHG and the minimum was 90mmHG, with a range of 50, the mean was 115.6 (95% CI 113.9 – 117.3) with a standard deviation of +/- 13.4. When analyzing the diastolic blood pressure, the maximum blood pressure was 100mmHg and the minimum was 60mmHG, presenting a range of 40, the observed mean was 78.74 (95% CI 77.33 – 80.15) with a standard deviation of +/- 11.32 (see Graph 4).

Figure 4. Blood pressure of patients

Patients' blood pressure: Systolic $\bar{x}=115.6$; $\sigma = 13.4$. Diastolic $\bar{x}=78.74$; $\sigma = 11.32$. n=250.

were determined, and it was observed that 184 of the patients (73.6%) suffered from one or more comorbidities at the time of the study. When assessing comorbidities, it was observed

that 85 patients (34%) had a diagnosis of diabetes mellitus, 87 patients (34.8%) had a diagnosis of hypertension, 60 patients (24%) suffered from dyslipidemia, and 28 patients (11.2%) had another comorbidity (see Graph 5).

Figure 5. Patient comorbidities

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High blood pressure was observed most frequently with 34.8% of n: 250.

The degree of hepatic steatosis was determined by ultrasound, where it was observed that in 98 patients (39.3%) the degree

of hepatic steatosis was mild, in 83 patients (33.2%) it was observed that the steatosis was moderate and in 69 patients (27.6%) the degree of steatosis was severe (see Graph 6).

Figure 6. Degree of hepatic steatosis in patients

In this study, mild hepatic steatosis predominated with 39.3% of n: 250.

Cardiovascular risk was calculated using simple cardiac tomography, evaluating with the Agaston coronary calcium score, in which calcium plaques in the coronary arteries are assessed, where it was found that in 96 patients (38.4%) the

cardiovascular risk was very low, in 55 patients (22%) the risk was low, while in 61 patients (24.4%) the cardiovascular risk was moderate and in the remaining 38 patients (15.2%) the risk of presenting cardiovascular disease was severe (see Graph 7).

Figure 7. Cardiovascular risk of patients

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The most frequent cardiovascular risk was very low with 38.4% of n: 250.

The association of the degree of hepatic steatosis with the cardiovascular risk of the patients was carried out, where a statistically significant association was found with a p=

0.046, observing that mild and moderate hepatic steatosis predominated in patients who presented a very low cardiovascular risk, while severe hepatic steatosis was observed more frequently in patients with moderate cardiovascular risk (see Table 1).

Table 1. Relationship between hepatic steatosis and cardiovascular risk

	Cardiovascular risk								p*	
	Very low		Low		Moderate		Serious			
	F	%	F	%	F	%	F	%		
Hepatic steatosis										
-Mild	40	16.00	19	7.60	22	8.80	17	6.80	0.046	
-Moderate	40	16.00	19	7.60	16	6.40	8	3.20		
-Severe	16	6.40	17	6.80	23	9.20	13	5.20		

*p-value obtained from χ^2

χ^2 : 12.82

p: 0.046

DISCUSSION

In this study of 250 patients with hepatic steatosis, 56.6% were found to be female, with a mean age of 50.02 years and a standard deviation of +/- 16.89. In contrast, the study "Coronary artery disease and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease: clinical correlation using coronary calcium computed tomography" by Kirby RS et al., conducted in 2021, which studied 134 patients, had a mean age of 62 years with a standard deviation of +/- 9.1, and 65% of the population was male. (22)

When evaluating BMI, obesity was found to be predominant in this study group at 35.6%, while overweight was observed in 32% of the population. Regarding comorbidities, the two most frequent were hypertension and diabetes mellitus at 34.8% and 34%, respectively. Dyslipidemia was found to a lesser extent at 11.2%. In comparison, in 2022, the study "Factors associated with non-alcoholic fatty liver disease in patients from the rural area of the Chambo canton," conducted by Coello Viñan et al. in a population in Ecuador, found that 62.26% of patients were overweight or obese. Similarly, the predominant comorbidities were diabetes mellitus at 64.26%, hypertension at 52.83%, and dyslipidemia to a lesser extent at 49.06%. This confirms the importance of these comorbidities as factors related to hepatic steatosis. (5)

Regarding the degree of hepatic steatosis in the patients, mild steatosis was the most frequent finding at 39.3%, while when assessing cardiovascular risk, the most frequent was very low at 38.4%. However, when relating the degree of hepatic steatosis to cardiovascular risk, a statistically significant association was found (p = 0.046), indicating that a higher degree of hepatic steatosis was associated with a higher cardiovascular risk. Similarly, in the study "Association between non-alcoholic fatty liver disease and coronary calcification according to sex and obesity" conducted by Kim

Sh et al. in 2020, a population of 7,259 patients was studied. Hepatic steatosis was classified by ultrasound and coronary calcification by cardiac tomography. It was observed that 22.1% of the population presented mild steatosis, while up to 30.7% of the patients had coronary calcifications by tomography. When both variables were associated, a significant association was found in both obese participants (p = 0.011) and non-obese participants (p < 0.001). Similarly, Kirby RS et al., in their study "Coronary artery disease and non-alcoholic fatty liver disease: clinical correlation by coronary calcium computed tomography" published in 2021, found a statistically significant relationship between hepatic steatosis and coronary artery disease with a p= 0.02. (22,26)

CONCLUSIONS

According to the objective of this research, it can be concluded that cardiovascular risk is directly associated with the hepatic steatosis found in the patients, since when performing the analysis of both variables in the contingency table of χ^2 : 12.82, it was observed that the greater the degree of hepatic steatosis diagnosed by ultrasound, the greater the cardiovascular risk, obtaining a p value of 0.046, so the alternative hypothesis "Cardiovascular risk is associated with the degree of hepatic steatosis found in the patients" can be confirmed and the null hypothesis is rejected.

Regarding the specific objectives, it was found that in this study women predominated, and when classifying the BMI, a high frequency of overweight and obesity was found. Furthermore, it can be concluded that diabetes mellitus and high blood pressure are important factors in this pathology, since both in this study and in previous studies, a high frequency of both pathologies has been found as a comorbidity in patients with some degree of hepatic steatosis. When classifying the degree of hepatic steatosis and cardiovascular risk, mild hepatic steatosis and very low

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cardiovascular risk were found most frequently; however, both variables are statistically associated.

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APPENDIX 1. DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENT

Cardiovascular risk and hepatic steatosis in patients treated at a secondary level hospital.

Instructions:

I.- IDENTIFICATION DATA.

	NSS Folio	
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Name	Father's surname	Mother's surname	Sex	Age

Weight	KG

Size	MTS

BMI (value)				
Nutrition grade	1. Low weight (BMI < 18.5)	2. Normal weight (BMI 18.5 - 24.9)	3.- Overweight (BMI 25.0 - 29.9)	4.- Obesity (BMI ≥ 30.0)

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II.- DATA COLLECTION

Degree of hepatic steatosis	Grade I (mild) Grade II (moderate) Grade III (severe)		
Comorbidities	1.- Presence		2.- Absence
Type of Comorbidity	1.- Diabetes Mellitus	2.- HAS	3.- Dysdipidemia Other:
Systolic blood pressure	MMHG		
Coronary Calcium Score	0 no calcium plaque in coronary arteries.	Slight presence of calcium in coronary arteries: 1-100.	Moderate presence of calcium in coronary arteries; 101-400.
	Severe presence of calcium in coronary arteries >400		

MEXICAN SOCIAL SECURITY INSTITUTE
UNIT OF EDUCATION, RESEARCH AND HEALTH POLICY
HEALTH RESEARCH COORDINATION
INFORMED CONSENT LETTER

(ADULTS)

INFORMED CONSENT LETTER FOR PARTICIPATION IN RESEARCH PROTOCOLS

Study name: Association between calcium score and hepatic steatosis in patients treated at a level 2 hospital

External sponsor (if applicable): Not applicable.

Place and date: Orizaba, Veracruz, Mexico, 2025

Registration number: In process

Justification and objective of the study: Fat accumulation in the liver marks patients at high risk for developing coronary artery disease, which can have severe repercussions on their health if not identified in time through studies such as cardiac computed tomography.

The objective of this study is: To determine the association between coronary calcium score and hepatic steatosis disease in patients treated at the Regional General Hospital No. 1 of Orizaba, Veracruz. For cases already diagnosed with hepatic steatosis by ultrasound, the clinical record will be reviewed to determine the classification of hepatic steatosis. Subsequently, a simple cardiac tomography scan will be performed to identify calcium plaques in your coronary arteries, in order to determine your cardiovascular risk.

Procedures:

Possible risks and inconveniences: This research study does not represent any type of risk since the procedure to be performed is non-invasive.

Potential benefits you will receive by participating in the study: Not applicable

Information on results and treatment alternatives: In this case, the results will be provided to the Imaging Service, and if you wish to know your cardiovascular risk, you can request this information from the Imaging Service.

Participation or withdrawal: You are invited to participate in this study and may withdraw at any time.

Privacy and confidentiality: The results obtained are used confidentially only by the principal investigator, and the overall results may be published in scientific and/or educational journals, but in no way individually and much less with mention of the participants' names.

Availability of medical treatment for beneficiaries (if applicable): Not Applicable

Benefits upon completion of the study: Development of timely prevention and improvement strategies.

If you have any questions or need clarification regarding the study, you can contact:

Principal Investigator: Dr. Alfredo Cervantes Suarez, Registration Number: 98225275, Affiliation: UMF1, Tel : 2223630921, Email: alfrediux976@hotmail.com

Elisandro Fernandez Flores, registration number 97321356, affiliation: HGR No. 1, tel : 246 104 61 37, email nick_fernandez@live.com

Contributors: Not applicable

In case of doubts or clarifications you can contact the Clinical Coordination of Education and Research in Health (CCEIS) Telephone: 2727241500 of the General Regional Hospital No 1 Orizaba Veracruz Oriente 6 No 2115. Colonia Centro.

Cardiovascular Risk and Hepatic Steatosis in Patients Treated at A Level 2 Hospital.

_____ Name and signature of parent or Guardians or legal representative	_____ Dr. Elisandro Fernández Flores Name and signature of the person obtaining consent
_____ Witness 1 Name, address, relationship and signature	_____ Witness 2 Name, address, relationship and signature

Annex 2. INFORMED CONSENT